

Spectrally Efficient Time-Frequency Space Modulation: A Delay-Doppler Domain FTN Waveform for ISAC Systems

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Abstract—This paper introduces the *spectrally efficient time-frequency space (SETFS) modulation*, a *two-dimensional (2D) modulation* extending the concepts of *spectrally efficient frequency division multiplexing (SEFDM)* and *orthogonal time-frequency space (OTFS) modulation* by increasing the spectral overlap at two levels, i.e., between subcarriers and sub-bands. This double compression improves the use of the available spectrum. Moreover, in SETFS, the periodicity in both time and frequency is maintained through the use of a *double cyclic prefix (DCP)* in order to simplify channel equalization and avoid 2D inter-symbol interference (ISI). However, the presence of a spectral overlap induces 2D *inter-carrier interference (ICI)*, that makes symbol detection more complicated. To mitigate channel estimation errors and also support high-resolution sensing, a novel channel estimator, dubbed *Newton-based estimation and spectral cancellation algorithm (NESCA)* is proposed. Numerical results show that SETFS achieves up to a 19% gain in the achievable communication rate with respect to OTFS at the cost of higher receiver complexity. Moreover, SETFS combined with NESCA provides near optimum performance in delay and Doppler estimation compared to other two techniques, thus offering a favorable trade-off between spectral efficiency, computational complexity, and sensing accuracy.

Index Terms—Channel Estimation, Detection, Faster-than-Nyquist, Orthogonal Time-Frequency Space, Spectral Efficiency

I. INTRODUCTION

With the advent of the *sixth-generation (6G)* of wireless communications, *integrated sensing and communication (ISAC)* has emerged as a key paradigm to enhance *spectral efficiency (SE)* while simultaneously enabling a wide range of sensing-oriented applications. A crucial challenge in ISAC is the design of waveforms able to offer good performance in both communication and sensing under specific spectral and complexity constraints [1]. Additionally, as carrier frequencies continue to increase, signal propagation may be substantially affected by Doppler shifts and time-variant channel effects; this can severely degrade the performance of traditional mul-

ticarrier modulations such as *orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM)* [2].

Recently, to overcome the last limitation, *orthogonal time-frequency space (OTFS)* modulation has been proposed as a promising alternative to OFDM, thanks to its inherent robustness against Doppler effects and its ability to provide full *time-frequency (TF)* diversity [3], [4]. OTFS maps information symbols in the *delay-Doppler (DD)* domain and relies on the *discrete symplectic Fourier transform (DSFT)* to spread each symbol across all TF resources. When implemented with a *double cyclic prefix (DCP)* [5], the channel filtering results in a *two-dimensional (2D) cyclic convolution* in the DD domain, equivalent to an element-wise multiplication in the TF domain. This property ensures the absence of *inter-symbol interference (ISI)* between adjacent OTFS symbols and enables simple single-tap equalization. Moreover, channel estimation can be efficiently performed through the transmission of a single OTFS pilot symbol at the beginning of each frame [6].

In this work, we extend the concept of spectrally efficient multicarrier modulation, originally introduced in *one-dimensional (1D) frequency-domain (FD)* modulations such as *spectrally efficient frequency division multiplexing (SEFDM)* [7]–[9], to the 2D OTFS framework. More specifically, we introduce novel modulation format, dubbed *spectrally efficient time-frequency space (SETFS)*, which generalizes SEFDM to the DD domain. Unlike conventional OTFS, SETFS intentionally increases the spectral overlap at two levels, namely between subcarriers and sub-bands, thus breaking the orthogonality in both time and frequency while achieving higher SE.

To the best of our knowledge, no prior work has investigated such a non-orthogonal 2D modulation. The closest related studies concern *multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) faster-than-Nyquist (FTN)* signaling for OTFS systems, where the lack of orthogonality is introduced across antennas, while the underlying modulation remains orthogonal [10], [11]. In contrast, in this work we introduce SETFS modulation as a generalization of the SEFDM concept to the 2D OTFS framework, including the use of both *time-domain (TD)* and *FD cyclic prefixes (CPs)* in its generation (i.e., a *double cyclic prefix, DCP*). The resulting modulation format ensures cyclicity in both time and frequency, and, similarly as OTFS-DCP, allows for simple element-wise equalization, so avoiding

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the need for higher-complexity *decision-feedback equalization* (DFE) techniques (e.g. see [12] for *zero-padded*, ZP OTFS). However, unlike OTFS-DCP, the spectral compression introduces intentional 2D ICI, which breaks the full orthogonality of the modulation. As a result, additional detection complexity is required at the receiver to properly recover the transmitted symbols while preserving the SE gain [8], [9].

The main contribution of this manuscript is threefold and can be summarized as follows:

1) We propose a novel modulation scheme, named SETFS, which extends SEFDM through the use of *fractional discrete symplectic Fourier transform* (FrDSFT) and of proper pulse shaping (*root-raised cosine*, RRC, pulses).

2) We develop a low-complexity SETFS baseband transceiver architecture, including channel estimation via a single SETFS pilot symbol, single-tap *minimum mean square error* (MMSE) equalization and *message-passing* (MP) detection adapted from SEFDM systems [9].

3) We develop a novel channel refinement algorithm, named *Newton-based estimation and spectral cancellation algorithm* (NESCA), which estimates the channel parameters (namely, the delays, Doppler shifts, amplitudes, and overall number of paths) to reconstruct a denoised channel representation with the aim of improving the subsequent equalization accuracy.

The rest of this manuscript is organized as follows: in Section II, the main steps for the generation of the SETFS signal are sketched and the baseband models for the *received* (RX) signal in the presence of a doubly selective channel are illustrated. Section III is devoted to the development of the NESCA, whereas its performance is compared with the conventional and widely employed *periodogram method* (also employed in the OFDM and OTFS literature; e.g., see [1], [3]) in Section IV. Data detection performance for SETFS are compared with that achieved by OTFS-DCP in terms of achievable capacity when the *parallel-branch message passing algorithm* (PBMPA) developed in [9] is employed for SETFS after channel equalization to recover the intentional ICI introduced by compression. Finally, some conclusions are offered in Section V.

Notation: In this paper, the following notation is adopted: 1) $(\cdot)^*$ and $(\cdot)^H$ denote complex conjugate and complex conjugate transpose, respectively; 2) the symbols \odot and \oslash represent the Hadamard and product and division operators, respectively; 3) the symbols \otimes and \circledast represent the Kronecker and Khatri-Rao product operators, respectively; 4) $\text{mod}_N[\cdot]$ indicates the *modulo N* operator; 5) $\mathbf{X} \triangleq [x_{m,n}]$ defines a matrix \mathbf{X} of proper size and $x_{m,n}$ denotes the element appearing on its m th row and n th column; 6) $\mathbf{y} = \text{vec}(\mathbf{Y})$ defines an (MN) -dimensional column vector resulting from the ordered concatenation of the columns of the $M \times N$ matrix \mathbf{Y} ; 7) $\Re\{x\}$ indicates the *real part* of the complex variable x ; 8) $\mathbf{0}_N$ denotes the zero vector of size N ; 9) Ξ_N indicates the unitary *discrete Fourier transform* (DFT) matrix of size N , whose (p, q) element is $\exp(-j2\pi pq/N)\sqrt{N}$.

II. SIGNAL AND SYSTEM MODELS

In this section, we focus on the derivation of an analytical model for the complex envelope of the transmitted SETFS signal and of the corresponding received signal in the presence of a doubly selective fading channel.

The baseband architecture of the proposed SETFS-based communication system is illustrated in Fig. 1. In the following, we assume that the SETFS signal conveys the $M \times N$ matrix $\mathbf{C} \triangleq [c_{m,n}]$ (with $m = 0, 1, \dots, M-1$ and $n = 0, 1, \dots, N-1$) containing N_u channel symbols belonging to an M_c -ary constellation and $N_{sc} \triangleq MN - N_u$ zeroes (associated with the *suppressed carriers*, SCs).

Our derivation of the SETFS signal model parallels that provided in [5, Sec. II-C] for an OTFS-DCP signal; the main difference is represented by the fact that the matrix \mathbf{C} undergoes an order (M, N) *fractional inverse discrete symplectic Fourier transform* (FrIDSFT) of (positive) parameters $(\beta^{(\text{FD})}, \beta^{(\text{TD})})$ both less than or equal to one (note that, if $(\beta^{(\text{FD})}, \beta^{(\text{TD})}) = (1, 1)$, SETFS coincides with OTFS); this produces

$$\mathbf{X} \triangleq [x_{m,n}] = \mathbf{F}_{M, \beta^{(\text{FD})}} \mathbf{C} \mathbf{F}_{N, \beta^{(\text{TD})}}^H, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{F}_{X, \beta}$ is a square matrix of order X , whose (p, q) th element is equal to $\exp(-j2\pi pq\beta/X)/\sqrt{X}$. The matrix \mathbf{X} , in (1), is *cyclically extended along both dimensions*, with period N in the index n (i.e., in the TD) and period M in the index m (i.e., in the FD); the new elements are generated as $x_{k,l} = x_{\text{mod}_M[k], \text{mod}_N[l]}$ for $k \notin \{0, 1, \dots, M-1\}$ and $l \notin \{0, 1, \dots, N-1\}$. This results in the introduction of a TD CP, a FD CP and a FD *cyclic postfix* (CPO) having sizes $N_{\text{cp}}^{(\text{TD})}$, $N_{\text{cp}}^{(\text{FD})}$ and $N_{\text{cpo}}^{(\text{FD})}$, respectively.

The complex envelope of the SETFS signal conveying the cyclically extended symbol can be expressed in a similar way as that of OTFS-DCP, i.e., as (see [5, Eq. (62)])

$$s(t; \mathbf{C}) = \sum_{k=-(M/2+N_{\text{cp}}^{(\text{FD})})}^{M/2+N_{\text{cpo}}^{(\text{FD})}-1} s_k^{(\text{TD})}(t; \mathbf{C}), \quad (2)$$

where

$$s_k^{(\text{TD})}(t; \mathbf{C}) \triangleq \sum_{l=-N_{\text{cp}}^{(\text{TD})}}^{N-1} x_{k,l} p(t - lT_s/\beta^{(\text{TD})}) \cdot \exp(j2\pi k B_s \beta^{(\text{FD})} (t - lT_s/\beta^{(\text{TD})})). \quad (3)$$

It is important to point out that $s_k^{(\text{TD})}(t; \mathbf{C})$ (3) can be interpreted as the frequency-shifted version of a SEFDM signal (e.g., see [9, Eq. (2)]), characterized by a CP of size $N_{\text{cp}}^{(\text{TD})}$, TX pulse $p(t)$, symbol interval T_s and a frequency shift equal to $k B_s \beta^{(\text{FD})}$, where B_s represents, up to the compression factor $\beta^{(\text{FD})}$, the frequency spacing between adjacent SEFDM signals. This observation suggests to adopt the same pulse and the same rules for subcarrier suppression as in SEFDM (see [9]). This leads to: 1) selecting $p(t)$ as a pulse whose spectrum $P(f)$ is the RRC with *roll-off factor* $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ [5, Eq. (17)]; 2)

Fig. 1. Baseband model of the considered SETFS-based communication system.

meeting the condition $B_s \beta^{(\text{FD})} = \beta^{(\text{TD})}/T_s$; 3) setting to zero multiple (i.e., N_{sc}) elements of the matrix \mathbf{C} . Based on the last choices and on its cyclic structure, the signal $s_k^{(\text{TD})}(t; \mathbf{C})$ (3) can be represented through its *Fourier series* (FS) as

$$s_k^{(\text{TD})}(t; \mathbf{C}) = \sum_{q=-\infty}^{+\infty} S_{k,q}^{(\text{TD})}(\mathbf{C}) \exp(j2\pi f_q t) \quad (4)$$

in the interval $[0, T']$, with $T' \triangleq NT_s/\beta^{(\text{TD})}$; here, $f_q \triangleq q/T'$ the q th SEFDM subcarrier frequency. Moreover, in (4),

$$S_{k,q}^{(\text{TD})}(\mathbf{C}) = \frac{\beta^{(\text{TD})}}{\sqrt{NT_s}} X_{k,q} P\left(\frac{q-kN}{T'}\right) \quad (5)$$

is the q th Fourier coefficient of $s_k^{(\text{TD})}(t; \mathbf{C})$ (3) and

$$X_{k,q} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x_{k,n} \exp(-j2\pi q \frac{n}{N}). \quad (6)$$

is the q th coefficient of the order N DFT of the sequence $\{x_{k,n}\}$ with respect to the index n .

Let us assume now the signal $s(t; \mathbf{C})$ (2) is sent over a doubly selective fading channel, having *channel impulse response* (CIR)

$$h(t, \tau) = \sum_{l=0}^{L-1} a_l \exp(j2\pi \nu_l t) \delta(\tau - \tau_l), \quad (7)$$

characterized by the L triplets $\{(a_l, \tau_l, \nu_l); l = 0, 1, \dots, L-1\}$; here, a_l , τ_l and ν_l represent the gain, the delay¹ and the Doppler shift associated with the l th path, respectively and L is the overall number of paths. The baseband equivalent of the received signal $r(t; \mathbf{C})$ feeds a *filter bank*, consisting of M distinct *matched filters* (see [5, eq. (99)]). The response of the \tilde{k} th matched filter (with $\tilde{k} = -M/2, -M/2+1, \dots, M/2-1$), having impulse response

$$\phi_{\tilde{k}}(t) = p^*(-t) \exp(j2\pi \tilde{k} t \beta^{(\text{TD})}/T_s), \quad (8)$$

is sampled at the instant $t_{\tilde{n}} = \tau_{L-1} + \tilde{n}T_s$, with $\tilde{n} = 0, 1, \dots, N-1$; this produces the sample $r[\tilde{k}, \tilde{n}]$. The MN samples acquired at the output of the filter bank are collected in the $M \times N$ matrix $\mathbf{R} \triangleq [r[\tilde{k}, \tilde{n}]]$. In [5, Sec. II-C.4], it is proved that the property of double periodicity, ensured by the

introduction of a DCP, and the specific choice of the pulse $p(t)$ allows to express \mathbf{R} as

$$\mathbf{R} \triangleq \mathbf{H} \odot \mathbf{T}(\mathbf{C}) + \mathbf{W}; \quad (9)$$

here, $\mathbf{H} \triangleq [h[\tilde{k}, \tilde{n}]]$ and $\mathbf{W} \triangleq [w[\tilde{k}, \tilde{n}]]$ are $M \times N$ matrices that represent the *channel state information* (CSI) and the complex noise matrix affecting \mathbf{R} (an *additive white Gaussian noise*, AWGN, model is assumed for the 2D sequence $\{w[\tilde{k}, \tilde{n}]\}$; the variance of noise samples is denoted σ_w^2), respectively. Additionally,

$$h[\tilde{k}, \tilde{n}] \triangleq \sum_{l=0}^{L-1} A_l \exp(-j2\pi \tilde{k} F_{\tau_l}) \exp(j2\pi \tilde{n} F_{\nu_l}), \quad (10)$$

with $\tilde{k} = 0, 1, \dots, M-1$ and $\tilde{n} = 0, 1, \dots, N-1$, $A_l \triangleq a_l \exp(j2\pi \nu_l (\tau_l + \tau_{L-1}))$, $F_{\tau_l} \triangleq (\tau_l - \tau_{L-1})\beta^{(\text{TD})}/T_s$ and $F_{\nu_l} \triangleq \nu_l/(B_s \beta^{(\text{FD})})$ represent the complex gain, the *normalized delay* and *normalized Doppler shift* associated with the l th channel path, respectively and (see (9))

$$\mathbf{T}(\mathbf{C}) = \mathbf{F}_{M, \beta^{(\text{FD})}}(\mathbf{C} \odot \bar{\mathbf{G}}) \mathbf{F}_{N, \beta^{(\text{TD})}}^H, \quad (11)$$

is an $M \times N$ matrix accounting for the channel symbols through \mathbf{C} and the pulse shape through $\bar{\mathbf{G}} \triangleq [\bar{g}_{p,q}]$. As shown in [5, eq. (82)], $\bar{g}_{p,q}$ exhibits a weak dependence on the normalized frequencies F_{τ_l} and F_{ν_l} . For this reason, the coefficients $\{\bar{g}_{p,q}\}$ corresponding to the N_u unsuppressed channel symbols are characterized by similar amplitudes (in particular, by a unitary amplitude). This property significantly simplifies channel estimation, equalization and subsequent data detection. These steps are described in the next section.

III. RECEIVER OPERATIONS

This section is organized into two parts. The first part revisits the channel estimation, equalization, and data detection stages, which constitute the core of the receiver processing chain. The second part focuses on the derivation of a novel Newton-based algorithm for the estimation of channel parameters, which is able to provide a refined reconstruction of the channel response. While the first part is essential to ensure reliable data recovery, the second provides a more detailed channel characterization. Note that, such parameter estimation not only improves communication performance at the receiver, but can also be exploited in *co-located* ISAC systems to enable radar sensing capabilities.

¹We assume the CIR components are arranged in ascending order of delays, so that τ_0 and τ_{L-1} represent the minimum and maximum delays, respectively.

A. Channel Estimation, Equalization & Detection

We first consider the transmission of a SETFS frame consisting of D SETFS symbols, the first serving as a *pilot*. In the following the SETFS pilot symbol² is denoted \mathbf{C}_0 , whereas the remaining SETFS symbols are $\{\mathbf{C}_d \triangleq [c_{m,n}^{(d)}]; d = 1, 2, \dots, D-1\}$; moreover, the RX signal matrix \mathbf{R} (9) associated with the d th SETFS symbol is denoted \mathbf{R}_d . In addition, we assume that: 1) all the elements of the matrix \mathbf{R}_d (9) are affected by AWGN with variance σ_w^2 for any d ; 2) \mathbf{C}_0 contains a single non-null pilot channel symbol, belonging to the unsuppressed region of \mathbf{C} (the remaining elements of the SETFS pilot symbol are equal to zero); 3) the channel variations over each SETFS frame can be deemed negligible; 4) thanks to the last assumption, CSI can be estimated on the basis of \mathbf{C}_0 and, then, be exploited for channel equalization over the other $(D-1)$ SETFS symbol intervals of the same frame.

The estimate $\hat{\mathbf{H}}$ of \mathbf{H} is evaluated as

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}} \triangleq [\hat{h}[\tilde{k}, \tilde{n}]] = \mathbf{R}_0 \odot \mathbf{T}(\mathbf{C}^{(0)}), \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{T}(\mathbf{C}^{(0)})$ is known at receive side (see (11) with $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{C}^{(0)}$). Note that the CSI estimate achieved through (12) can also be directly exploited to equalize the remaining $(D-1)$ SETFS symbols in the TF domain. In particular, equalization can be accomplished in the TF domain to compensate for the distortions introduced by the channel (see (9)). The d th MMSE equalized matrix is computed as

$$\hat{\mathbf{T}}_d \triangleq \hat{\mathbf{T}}(\mathbf{C}^{(d)}) = \mathbf{R}_d \odot \mathbf{Q}_{\text{mmse}}, \quad (13)$$

where $\mathbf{Q}_{\text{mmse}} \triangleq [q[\tilde{k}, \tilde{n}]]$ is an $M \times N$ matrix, whose (\tilde{k}, \tilde{n}) th element is $q[\tilde{k}, \tilde{n}] \triangleq \hat{h}^*[\tilde{k}, \tilde{n}] / (\hat{h}^*[\tilde{k}, \tilde{n}] \hat{h}[\tilde{k}, \tilde{n}] + \hat{\sigma}_w^2)$, with $\hat{\sigma}_w^2$ being an estimate of the noise variance in (9).

To ease our description of symbol detection, we rewrite the expression (11) in vector form for the d th SETFS data symbol as

$$\gamma_d \triangleq \text{vec}(\mathbf{T}(\mathbf{C}^{(d)})) = \Psi_{\beta^{(\text{FD})}, \beta^{(\text{TD})}}^H \bar{\mathbf{c}}_d, \quad (14)$$

with $d = 1, 2, \dots, D-1$; here, $\Psi_{\beta^{(\text{FD})}, \beta^{(\text{TD})}} \triangleq \mathbf{F}_{N, \beta^{(\text{TD})}} \otimes \mathbf{F}_{M, \beta^{(\text{FD})}}^H$ is an $(MN) \times (MN)$ matrix and $\bar{\mathbf{c}}_d \triangleq \text{vec}(\mathbf{C}^{(d)}) \odot \bar{\mathbf{G}}$ is an (MN) -dimensional vector. In fact, detection can be accomplished on a *symbol-by-symbol* basis by first applying the order (M, N) FrDSFT of parameters $(\beta^{(\text{FD})}, \beta^{(\text{TD})})$ to $\hat{\gamma}_d \triangleq \text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{T}}_d)$ (see (13)); this produces

$$\hat{\mathbf{c}}_d = \mathbf{\Gamma} \bar{\mathbf{c}}_d + \check{\mathbf{w}}, \quad (15)$$

where $\mathbf{\Gamma} \triangleq \Psi_{\beta^{(\text{FD})}, \beta^{(\text{TD})}} \Psi_{\beta^{(\text{FD})}, \beta^{(\text{TD})}}^H$ is the $(MN) \times (MN)$ matrix accounting the 2D intentional ICI introduced by spectral compression. Detecting the channel symbols in (15) requires compensating for the intentional 2D ICI represented by $\mathbf{\Gamma}$. In this work, the detection stage is not explicitly addressed; instead, we rely on the PBMPA detector proposed in [9] for a SEFDM-based communication system, since the signal model and the structure of the ICI matrix $\mathbf{\Gamma}$ in (15) are similar (see [9, Eq. (7)]).

²The considered pilot rate is thus $1/D$.

B. Channel parameter estimation algorithm

In this section, we focus on the problem of estimating the parameters of the communication channel, namely a) the set of parameters $\{(A_l, F_{\tau_l}, F_{\nu_l}); l = 0, 1, \dots, L-1\}$ and b) the number of paths L , which completely describe the matrix \mathbf{H} (see (10)). The availability of an estimate $\hat{\mathbf{H}}$ of the channel \mathbf{H} (see (10)) is assumed. To begin, we rewrite the model (12) in vector form as

$$\hat{\mathbf{h}} \triangleq \text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{H}}) = \mathbf{h} + \mathbf{w}, \quad (16)$$

where \mathbf{w} is the (MN) -dimensional column vector of noise samples affecting $\hat{\mathbf{h}}$, whereas

$$\mathbf{h} \triangleq \text{vec}(\mathbf{H}) = \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{f}_\tau, \mathbf{f}_\nu) \mathbf{a}; \quad (17)$$

here, $\mathbf{a} \triangleq [A_0, A_1, \dots, A_{L-1}]^T$, $\mathbf{f}_\tau \triangleq [F_{\tau_0}, F_{\tau_1}, \dots, F_{\tau_{L-1}}]^T$ and $\mathbf{f}_\nu \triangleq [F_{\nu_0}, F_{\nu_1}, \dots, F_{\nu_{L-1}}]^T$ collect the L complex gains, normalized delays and normalized Doppler frequencies, respectively. Moreover, in (17),

$$\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{f}_\tau, \mathbf{f}_\nu) \triangleq \mathbf{C}_N^*(\mathbf{f}_\nu) \otimes \mathbf{C}_M(\mathbf{f}_\tau) \quad (18)$$

is an $(MN) \times L$ matrix, $\mathbf{C}_p(\mathbf{f}) \triangleq [\bar{\mathbf{b}}_0(\mathbf{f}), \bar{\mathbf{b}}_1(\mathbf{f}), \dots, \bar{\mathbf{b}}_{p-1}(\mathbf{f})]^T$ is a $p \times L$ matrix for any positive integer p , $\bar{\mathbf{b}}_x(\mathbf{f}) \triangleq [\bar{b}_x(f_0), \bar{b}_x(f_1), \dots, \bar{b}_x(f_{L-1})]^T$ is an L -dimensional column vector and $\bar{b}_x(f_l) \triangleq \exp(-j2\pi x f_l)$ for any l .

Given $\hat{\mathbf{h}}$ (16), our goal is estimating \mathbf{a} , \mathbf{f}_τ , \mathbf{f}_ν and L . The algorithm we propose is dubbed NESCA and consists of four steps: 1) an initialization step based on the computation of the 2D spectrum of $\hat{\mathbf{h}}$; 2) a residual spectrum maximization step; 3) a Newton-based frequency refinement and 4) a spectral cancellation procedure. Each of the four steps is briefly described in the following

Step 1 - The *initialization step* consists in:

1) evaluating the 2D spectral matrix (through a *discrete symplectic Fourier transform*, DSFT)

$$\mathbf{Y} \triangleq [y[\tilde{m}, \tilde{n}]] = L_r L_c \Xi_{M_0}^H \hat{\mathbf{H}}_{\text{ZP}} \Xi_{N_0} \quad (19)$$

where

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{\text{ZP}} \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{H}}, & (\mathbf{0}_M \mathbf{0}_{N_0-N}^T) \\ (\mathbf{0}_{M_0-M} \mathbf{0}_N^T) & (\mathbf{0}_{M_0-M} \mathbf{0}_{N_0-N}^T) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (20)$$

is the ZP version of $\hat{\mathbf{H}}$; the last matrix has size $M_0 \times N_0$, where $M_0 \triangleq L_r M$ and $N_0 \triangleq L_c N$, with L_r and L_c being the *oversampling factors*, for the rows of $\hat{\mathbf{H}}$ and its columns, respectively (12).

2) Initializing the *residual spectrum* $\mathbf{Y}_{\text{res}} \triangleq [y_{\text{res}}[\tilde{k}, \tilde{n}]] = \mathbf{Y}$ and the parameter $\bar{L} = 0$.

Step 2 - The residual spectrum energy $\|\mathbf{Y}_{\text{res}}\|^2$ is evaluated; if this quantity is greater than or equal to³ a given detection threshold ϵ , \bar{L} is increased by one and the parameters associated with a new (i.e., the $(\bar{L}-1)$ th) 2D tone are estimated as

$$\hat{F}_{\tau_{\bar{L}-1}} = \hat{m}/M_0, \quad (21)$$

³If this condition is not met, the algorithm stops and the \bar{L} -dimensional estimate vectors of the channel parameters are provided as output.

$$\hat{F}_{\nu_{\bar{L}-1}} = \hat{n}/N_0 - 0.5 \quad (22)$$

and

$$\hat{A}_{\bar{L}-1} = y_{\text{res}}[\hat{m}, \hat{n}], \quad (23)$$

where (see (19))

$$(\hat{m}, \hat{n}) = \arg \max_{\tilde{m}, \tilde{n}} |y_{\text{res}}[\tilde{m}, \tilde{n}]|. \quad (24)$$

Step 3 - The third step is fed by \bar{L} -dimensional vectors $\hat{\mathbf{a}} \triangleq [\hat{A}_0, \hat{A}_1, \dots, \hat{A}_{\bar{L}-1}]^T$, $\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau \triangleq [\hat{F}_{\tau_0}, \hat{F}_{\tau_1}, \dots, \hat{F}_{\tau_{\bar{L}-1}}]^T$ and $\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu \triangleq [\hat{F}_{\nu_0}, \hat{F}_{\nu_1}, \dots, \hat{F}_{\nu_{\bar{L}-1}}]^T$, collecting the estimates of the complex gains, normalized delays and normalized Doppler frequencies, respectively, with $\bar{L} \leq L$. It refines these estimates through an iterative procedure, which maximizes, in an approximate fashion, the *maximum likelihood* (ML) cost function

$$p(\hat{\mathbf{h}}|\hat{\mathbf{a}}, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu) = \frac{1}{(\pi\sigma_w^2)^{MN}} \exp(-\mathcal{L}(\hat{\mathbf{h}}|\hat{\mathbf{a}}, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu)/\sigma_w^2). \quad (25)$$

In the last expression, the quantity

$$\mathcal{L}(\hat{\mathbf{h}}|\hat{\mathbf{a}}, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu) \triangleq \|\hat{\mathbf{h}} - \mathbf{B}(\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu) \hat{\mathbf{a}}\|^2 \quad (26)$$

is the *log-likelihood* (LL) function of the considered optimization problem. The refinement procedure is initialized by setting $\hat{\mathbf{a}}^{(0)} = \hat{\mathbf{a}}$, $\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau^{(0)} = \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau$ and $\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu^{(0)} = \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu$, $\hat{\mathbf{f}}^{(0)} = [(\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau^{(0)})^T, (\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu^{(0)})^T]^T$ and the iteration index i set to 1. Then, an iterative procedure, is started; it consists in:

1) *A Complex amplitude update* – The new complex amplitude vector

$$\hat{\mathbf{a}}^{(i)} = \mathbf{B}^\dagger(\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau^{(i-1)}, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu^{(i-1)}) \hat{\mathbf{h}} \quad (27)$$

is computed; here, $\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau^{(i-1)}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu^{(i-1)}$ denote the estimates of $\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau$ and $\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu$ at the end of the $(i-1)$ th iteration.

2) *A Frequency update* – The new estimate

$$\hat{\mathbf{f}}^{(i)} = \hat{\mathbf{f}}^{(i-1)} - \mu \ddot{\mathbf{H}}_{\mathcal{L}}^{-1}(\hat{\mathbf{a}}^{(i)}, \hat{\mathbf{f}}^{(i-1)}) \nabla_{\mathcal{L}}(\hat{\mathbf{a}}^{(i)}, \hat{\mathbf{f}}^{(i-1)}) \quad (28)$$

is evaluated; here, $\hat{\mathbf{f}}^{(i)} = [(\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau^{(i)})^T, (\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu^{(i)})^T]^T$, μ is a (positive) step size (in our simulations, this parameter has been set to one), and $\nabla_{\mathcal{L}}(\hat{\mathbf{a}}, \hat{\mathbf{f}})$ and $\ddot{\mathbf{H}}_{\mathcal{L}}(\hat{\mathbf{a}}, \hat{\mathbf{f}})$ represent, for a given couple $(\hat{\mathbf{a}}, \hat{\mathbf{f}})$ the *gradient* vector and *Hessian* matrix of the LL function \mathcal{L} (26). The gradient and the Hessian of \mathcal{L} can be expressed as⁴

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{\mathcal{L}}(\hat{\mathbf{a}}, \hat{\mathbf{f}}) &= -2 \left[\Re\{\tilde{\mathbf{a}}^* \odot \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau}^H(\hat{\mathbf{h}} - \mathbf{B}\hat{\mathbf{a}})\}^T, \right. \\ &\quad \left. \Re\{\tilde{\mathbf{a}}^* \odot \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu}^H(\hat{\mathbf{h}} - \mathbf{B}\hat{\mathbf{a}})\}^T \right]^T, \quad (29) \end{aligned}$$

and as

$$\ddot{\mathbf{H}}_{\mathcal{L}}(\hat{\mathbf{a}}, \hat{\mathbf{f}}) \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{T}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau} & \mathbf{U}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu} \\ \mathbf{U}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau} & \mathbf{V}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (30)$$

⁴The dependence of the matrix \mathbf{B} (18) on the variables $(\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu)$ is not explicitly shown in the following to ease reading.

respectively; here⁵,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{T}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau} &\triangleq \left[\frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{L}}{\partial \hat{f}_{\tau_i} \partial \hat{f}_{\tau_{i'}}} \right] = 2\Re\left\{ (\tilde{\mathbf{a}} \tilde{\mathbf{a}}^H) \odot \left(\dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau}^H \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau}^* \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \left(\tilde{\mathbf{a}}^* (\hat{\mathbf{h}} - \mathbf{B}\tilde{\mathbf{a}})^H \ddot{\mathbf{B}}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau} \right) \right\}, \quad (31) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{U}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu} &\triangleq \left[\frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{L}}{\partial \hat{f}_{\tau_i} \partial \hat{f}_{\nu_{i'}}} \right] = 2\Re\left\{ (\tilde{\mathbf{a}} \tilde{\mathbf{a}}^H) \odot \left(\dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau}^H \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu}^* \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \left(\tilde{\mathbf{a}}^* (\hat{\mathbf{h}} - \mathbf{B}\tilde{\mathbf{a}})^H \ddot{\mathbf{B}}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu} \right) \right\} \quad (32) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{V}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu} &\triangleq \left[\frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{L}}{\partial \hat{f}_{\nu_i} \partial \hat{f}_{\nu_{i'}}} \right] = 2\Re\left\{ (\tilde{\mathbf{a}} \tilde{\mathbf{a}}^H) \odot \left(\dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu}^H \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu}^* \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \left(\tilde{\mathbf{a}}^* (\hat{\mathbf{h}} - \mathbf{B}\tilde{\mathbf{a}})^H \ddot{\mathbf{B}}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu} \right) \right\} \quad (33) \end{aligned}$$

are $\bar{L} \times \bar{L}$ matrices. Moreover, $\dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau}$ is an $(MN) \times \bar{L}$ matrix, whose l th column contains the partial derivative of the l th column of \mathbf{B} (see (18) with $(\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu) = (\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu)$), evaluated with respect to \hat{f}_x . Similarly, $\ddot{\mathbf{B}}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau}$ is a $(MN) \times \bar{L}$ matrix, whose l th column contains the second-order derivative of the l th column of \mathbf{B} (18) evaluated with respect to \hat{f}_x and \hat{f}_y . Note that, thanks to the linearity property of the derivative, the equality $\ddot{\mathbf{B}}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau} = \ddot{\mathbf{B}}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau}$ holds. A proof of the results illustrated above is sketched in Appendix A.

Step 4 - Once the refinement step for the \bar{L} 2D tones is completed, a spectral cancellation procedure is carried out; this step aims at computing the residual 2D $M_0 \times N_0$ spectrum

$$\mathbf{Y}_{\text{res}} \triangleq [y_{\text{res}}[\tilde{m}, \tilde{n}]] = \mathbf{Y} - \mathbf{Y}_c(\hat{\mathbf{a}}, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu), \quad (34)$$

where \mathbf{Y} is defined by (19). Moreover, in (34), $\mathbf{Y}_c(\hat{\mathbf{a}}, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu) \triangleq [y_c[\tilde{m}, \tilde{n}]]$ is an $M_0 \times N_0$ matrix, whose (\tilde{m}, \tilde{n}) th element is computed as

$$y_c[\tilde{m}, \tilde{n}] = \frac{1}{MN} \sum_{l=0}^{\bar{L}-1} \hat{A}_l \phi_{\tilde{m}}(\hat{F}_{\tau_l}, M_0) \phi_{\tilde{n}}^*(\hat{F}_{\nu_l}, N_0) \quad (35)$$

where

$$\phi_x(\hat{F}, X_0) \triangleq \frac{1 - \exp(j2\pi(x - F X_0))}{1 - \exp(j2\pi(\frac{x}{X_0} - F))} \quad (36)$$

with $x = 0, 1, \dots, X_0 - 1$ for any positive integer X_0 and normalized frequency F . This completes our description of last step of the NESCA. Note that: a) after spectral cancellation, the residual spectrum energy is evaluated again in **Step 2**; b) this step aims at improving estimation accuracy and may have a significant impact in the presence of multiple closely-spaced channel paths.

The NESCA algorithm is summarized in Algorithm 1. Its overall complexity, is $N_{\text{NESCA}} \cong N_{2\text{D-FFT}} + N_{\text{it}} L^2 MN$, where $N_{2\text{D-FFT}} = M_0 N_0 \log_2(M_0 N_0)$ is the complexity of the initialization (due to the evaluation of the 2D spectrum \mathbf{Y} (19)).

⁵Note that the dependence of the matrices $\mathbf{T}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau}$, $\mathbf{U}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\tau, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu}$ and $\mathbf{V}_{\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\nu}$ on the variable $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}$ is not explicitly shown to ease notation.

Algorithm 1: Newton-based estimation and spectral cancellation algorithm (NESCA)

Input: The $M \times N$ matrix $\hat{\mathbf{H}}$ (12), the detection threshold ϵ , the oversampling factors (L_r, L_c), the step size μ and the overall number of refinement iterations N_{it} .

- 1 **Initialization:** Compute \mathbf{Y} from $\hat{\mathbf{H}}$ through (19), set $\hat{\mathbf{a}}, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_{\tau_l}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{f}}_{\nu_l}$ to empty vectors and $\bar{L} = 0$. Initialize $\mathbf{Y}_{\text{res}} = \mathbf{Y}$.
 - 2 **Energy criterion:** If $\|\mathbf{Y}_{\text{res}}\|^2 \geq \epsilon$, then increase \bar{L} by one and go to step 3, otherwise go to **Output**.
 - 3 **Residual spectrum maximization:** Evaluate the new quantities $(\hat{A}_{\bar{L}-1}, \hat{F}_{\tau_{\bar{L}-1}}, \hat{F}_{\nu_{\bar{L}-1}})$, through (23), (21) and (22), using \mathbf{Y}_{res} in the spectral maximization (24). Then, append $\hat{F}_{\tau_{\bar{L}-1}}, \hat{F}_{\nu_{\bar{L}-1}}$ and $\hat{A}_{\bar{L}-1} = y_{\text{res}}[\hat{m}, \hat{n}]$ to $\hat{\mathbf{f}}_{\tau}, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_{\nu}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{a}}$, respectively.
 - 4 **Refinement:** Initialize $\hat{\mathbf{a}}^{(0)} = \hat{\mathbf{a}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{f}}^{(0)} = [\hat{\mathbf{f}}_{\tau}^T, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_{\nu}^T]^T$. **for** $i = 1$ **to** N_{it} **do**
 - 3a- *Amplitude update:* compute $\hat{\mathbf{a}}^{(i)}$ through (27).
 - 3b- *Frequency update:* Compute $\hat{\mathbf{f}}^{(i)} = [(\hat{\mathbf{f}}_{\tau}^{(i)})^T (\hat{\mathbf{f}}_{\nu}^{(i)})^T]^T$ using (28).**end**

Set $\hat{\mathbf{a}} = \hat{\mathbf{a}}^{(N_{\text{it}})}, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_{\tau} = \hat{\mathbf{f}}_{\tau}^{(N_{\text{it}})}, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_{\nu} = \hat{\mathbf{f}}_{\nu}^{(N_{\text{it}})}$ and $\hat{L} = \bar{L}$.
 - 5 **Spectral cancellation:** Update \mathbf{Y}_{res} through (34) using $\hat{\mathbf{a}}, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_{\tau}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{f}}_{\nu}$; then, go to step 2.
- Output:** The estimates $\hat{\mathbf{a}}, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_{\tau}, \hat{\mathbf{f}}_{\nu}$ and \hat{L} of $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{f}_{\tau}, \mathbf{f}_{\nu}$ and L , respectively.
-

TABLE I
COMPUTATIONAL COMPLEXITY ORDER OF THE CONSIDERED CHANNEL ESTIMATORS

Algorithm	$\mathcal{O}(\cdot)$
2D-FFT	$N_{2\text{D-FFT}}$
2D-FFTi	$N_{2\text{D-FFT}} + L(I_r I_c + \bar{M} \bar{N})$
NESCA	$N_{2\text{D-FFT}} + N_{\text{it}} L^2 M N$

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

Computer simulations have been run to assess the performance of the NESCA and to compare it with a) the *2D periodogram method* and b) with its variant including a refinement procedure based on interpolation of the 2D periodogram [13, Sec. IV-A]; these are dubbed 2D-FFT and 2D-FFTi in the following.

The computational complexity orders ($\mathcal{O}(\cdot)$) of the 2D-FFT algorithm, the 2D-FFTi algorithm and the NESCA are listed in Table I. Note that: 1) The 2D-FFT algorithm represents the baseline technique for the other two algorithms. 2) The 2D-FFTi refines each 2D frequency by interpolating the 2D spectral components around each peak detected by the 2D-FFT algorithm. The interpolation orders for the rows and columns of the 2D spectrum \mathbf{Y} (19) are denoted I_r and I_c , respectively. The interpolation procedure generates L finer 2D grids, each of size $\bar{M} \times \bar{N}$ and for which spectral maximization is carried

out to refine the L 2D frequencies and amplitudes. 3) The NESCA operates in an off-grid fashion and its complexity scales linearly with the variables M and N , and grows quadratically with the number of channel paths. However, since L is generally a small quantity, the major contribution to the complexity of the NESCA is given by its initialization step through the DSFT used to evaluate the 2D spectrum \mathbf{Y} (19).

In our simulations, *Gaussian quadrature rules* (GQR) [14] have been employed to generate a channel model approximating a doubly selective channel characterized by a truncated exponential power delay profile (maximum delay $\tau_{\text{max}} = 0.1\mu\text{s}$) and Jake's power spectrum for the Doppler effect (maximum Doppler shift $\nu_{\text{max}} = 178$ kHz). The resulted channel model has $L = 3$ paths, whose complex amplitudes are represented as the superposition of three complex exponentials. The following parameters have been selected for the SETFS frame and modulation format: 1) SETFS frame size $D = 8$; 2) $M = N = 32$ in the generation of each data matrix \mathbf{C} ; 3) subcarrier spacing $\Delta_f = 60$ kHz; 4) TD CP size $N_{\text{cp}}^{(\text{TD})} = N/4$; 5) FD CP and CPO sizes $N_{\text{cp}}^{(\text{FD})} = N_{\text{cpo}}^{(\text{FD})} = M/16$; 6) carrier frequency $f_c = 24$ GHz; 7) roll-off factor for the RRC pulse $\alpha = 0.15$; 8) cardinality of the *phase-shift keying* (PSK) constellation $M_c = 4$; 9) compression parameters $\beta^{(\text{TD})} = \beta^{(\text{FD})} = 0.9$. These choices result in: 1) channel symbol time $T_s \cong 0.5\mu\text{s}$; 2) frequency spacing between adjacent SEFDM symbols $B_s = 1.92$ MHz; 3) number of SCs for each SEFDM symbol $N_{\text{sc}} = 5$ (see comments above [5, Sec. II-A, Eq. (17)]); 4) useful bandwidth occupied by each SETFS symbol $B \triangleq M B_s = 61.4$ MHz; 5) delay and Doppler resolutions, $\tau_{\text{bin}} \triangleq T_s / (M \beta^{(\text{FD})}) \cong 16$ ns and $\nu_{\text{bin}} \triangleq B_s \beta^{(\text{TD})} / N \cong 60$ kHz. Note also that, from a communication perspective, the values selected for the parameters $(\beta^{(\text{FD})}, \beta^{(\text{TD})})$ have allowed us to achieve a good trade-off between SE and data detection complexity; in fact, reducing these two parameters improves SE, but increases the complexity of data detection because of the stronger ICI [8]. From a sensing perspective, instead, the values of $(\beta^{(\text{FD})}, \beta^{(\text{TD})})$ influence the 2D resolution grid; in fact, selecting smaller values for $(\beta^{(\text{FD})}, \beta^{(\text{TD})})$ entails a reduction in the spacing between normalized delays and an increase in that between normalized Doppler frequencies. This directly affects the achievable parameter estimation accuracy, as it modifies the related *Cramér-Rao lower bound* (CRLB).

The performance of the considered methods for channel parameter estimation has been compared in terms of *root mean square error* (RMSE) achieved for delay (RMSE $_{\tau}$) and Doppler shift (RMSE $_{\nu}$) estimation. The outcome $\{(\hat{A}_l, \hat{F}_{\tau_l}, \hat{F}_{\nu_l}); l = 0, 1, \dots, \hat{L} - 1\}$ of these algorithms is employed to reconstruct the channel estimates through (10), which are then used by the MMSE equalizer. After that, the PBMPA detector is used to recover the intentional 2D ICI due to compression. The communication performance is evaluated in terms of *effective capacity*, defined as $\mathcal{C}_{\text{eff}} \triangleq \text{MI} / (\beta^{(\text{TD})} \beta^{(\text{FD})})$, where the *mutual information* (MI) is

computed on the basis of the *soft-output* information generated by the considered detector. Note that [4, Eq. (54)] has been employed for the evaluation of the MI.

The performance of the proposed SETFS modulation has also been compared with that of a reference OTFS-DCP system, adopting the same SETFS parameters except for $\beta^{(\text{TD})}$ and $\beta^{(\text{FD})}$, which are both set to one. Additionally, a conventional *log-likelihood ratio* (LLR) detector operating after MMSE equalization has been employed for OTFS-DCP, since it allows symbol-by-symbol detection, providing soft-output information with low computational complexity. This setup provides a fair benchmark to assess the communication and sensing trade-offs of SETFS with respect to OTFS-DCP.

In generating our numerical results, the following choices have been made for all the considered algorithms: 1) the oversampling factors $L_r = L_c = 4$ have been used for 2D-FFT, 2D-FFTi and NESCA; 2) the overall number of paths L and the noise variance σ_w^2 have been assumed to be known at the receiver; 3) $N_{\text{it}} = 5$ and $\mu = 1$ have been selected for the NESCA. Additionally, the detection threshold ϵ has been always set to the 60% of the initial spectrum energy, i.e., $\sqrt{\|\mathbf{Y}\|^2}$ (see (19)); 4) in 2D-FFTi method, $I_r = I_c = 7$ have been selected and the 2D *spline* interpolation has been employed to generate finer spectral samples over $\bar{M} \times \bar{N}$ grid, with $\bar{M} = \bar{N} = 256$; 5) the PBMPA detector has been configured to perform 4 iterations.

Some results about RMSE_τ and RMSE_ν are shown in Fig. 2, for an $\text{SNR} \in [-10, 30]$ dB; the CRLB is also provided as a reference. The \mathcal{C}_{eff} performance achievable in the same SNR range using all the considered methods is shown in Fig. 3.

The results shown in Fig. 2 lead to the following conclusions:

1) An SNR threshold can be easily identified in all the RMSE curves; this threshold is approximately equal to 12 dB for all the considered algorithms.

2) Above the threshold, all the considered techniques achieve lower RMSE_τ when using SETFS with respect to OTFS-DCP. However, their RMSE_ν values are generally higher, suggesting less accurate Doppler estimation when employing SETFS. This trend is also reflected in the corresponding CRLBs; in particular, when OTFS-DCP is employed, the CRLB for delay estimation is higher, while that for Doppler estimation is lower than those observed with SETFS.

3) Both 2D-FFT and 2D-FFTi algorithms exhibit a RMSE floor at high SNRs (say, for an SNR higher than 20 dB). Keep in mind that, on the one hand, the 2D-FFT restricts the peak search to the 2D spectrum \mathbf{Y} (19); thus, its accuracy is limited by the Fourier transform orders. On the other hand, the 2D-FFTi employs a refinement step based on spectral interpolation and its accuracy is limited by the grid size.

4) Compared to the other methods, the NESCA achieves superior estimation accuracy (close to the CRLB) in terms of both RMSE_τ and RMSE_ν , while maintaining manageable complexity; this is mainly due to the fact that the NESCA algorithm operates in an off-grid fashion. It is also worth noting that its RMSE_τ tends to deviate from the respective

CRLBs at approximately 30 dB, while its RMSE_ν continues to follow the CRLB trend. This is due to the limited number of iterations carried out by the algorithm. Further simulations have evidenced that increasing N_{it} improves the NESCA RMSE performance at the price, however, of a higher computational complexity.

5) The computational complexity of the 2D-FFTi algorithm and NESCA is respectively 1.85 and 1.27 times higher than that of the 2D-FFT algorithm (see Table I); this means that the NESCA computational requirements are 27% higher than 2D-FFT and 46% lower than 2D-FFTi.

Finally, the results illustrated in Fig. 3 show that:

1) The LLR detector in OTFS-DCP is less sensitive to channel reconstruction errors and achieves similar performance when combined with 2D-FFT, 2D-FFTi and NESCA algorithm. Its complexity is approximately $\mathcal{O}(M_c)$.

2) SETFS modulation saturates approximately to a 19% higher \mathcal{C}_{eff} compared to OTFS-DCP thanks to spectral compression. However, this gain comes at the cost of a notably higher computational complexity⁶ of the PBMPA detector compared to the LLR detector; note that the last detector cannot be used for SETFS as it does not compensate for the 2D intentional ICI.

3) The NESCA combined with the PBMPA detector outperforms the other techniques for SETFS within the SNR range [10, 20] dB.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this manuscript, a novel modulation format, dubbed SETFS and generalizing the SEFDM paradigm to the 2D DD domain of OTFS, and a channel estimator, called NESCA, to be used in a SETFS-based communication system operating over a doubly selective fading channel, have been proposed. The SETFS modulation achieves significant SE gains, but requires an higher detection complexity than OTFS because of the presence of 2D ICI. Our simulation results show that NESCA achieves accurate channel parameter estimation, outperforming both 2D-FFT and 2D-FFTi (with a complexity 27% higher than 2D-FFT and 46% lower than 2D-FFTi), and closely approaching the CRLB in delay and Doppler estimation. It also outperforms the other two techniques, in terms of achievable communication rate, when combined with the PBMPA detector. In conclusion, SETFS modulation offers a promising trade-off between SE, complexity, and sensing performance, making it an potential candidate for future 6G ISAC systems. Our ongoing research activities in this field focus on the application of SETFS to more complex ISAC scenarios.

APPENDIX

A. Gradient and Hessian of the LL function

In this appendix, the derivation of the gradient (29) and of the Hessian matrix (30) for the cost function \mathcal{L} (26) is sketched. Before doing so, some basic properties of the

⁶Complexity increases approximately according to a factor NMM_c .

Fig. 2. Root mean square error performance achieved by 2D-FFT, the 2D-FFTi and NESCA in a) delay and b) Doppler shift estimation in the cases of SETFS with $(\beta^{(\text{FD})}, \beta^{(\text{TD})}) = (0.9, 0.9)$ (solid lines) and OTFS-DCP (dashed lines), for a variable SNR $\in [-10, 30]$ dB; the CLRBS are also shown.

Fig. 3. Effective capacity, C_{eff} , achieved by the PBMPA detector for SETFS with $(\beta^{(\text{FD})}, \beta^{(\text{TD})}) = (0.9, 0.9)$ (solid lines) when the MMSE equalizer employs the reconstructed channel generated through the estimates of the 2F-FFT, 2D-FFTi and NESCA. The performance offered by a LLR detector when OTFS-DCP is employed (i.e., $\beta^{(\text{TD})} = \beta^{(\text{FD})} = 1$) is also shown as a reference (dashed lines); moreover, Shannon capacity is included as it provides an upper bound. The SNR $\in [-10, 30]$ dB is considered.

Dirac vectors as well as of the stacking operations are illustrated. To this aim, we define: a) the L -dimensional vectors $\mathbf{x} \triangleq [x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{L-1}]^T$, $\mathbf{y} \triangleq [y_0, y_1, \dots, y_{L-1}]^T$ and $\mathbf{z} \triangleq [z_0, z_1, \dots, z_{L-1}]^T$ (the l th element is denoted x_l , y_l and z_l , respectively); b) the $L \times L$ matrix $\mathbf{A} \triangleq [a_{l,l'}]$ (its (l, l') th element is denoted $a_{l,l'}$); c) the L -dimensional vector $\delta_{L,l}$, called *Dirac vector*, having its l th element equal to unity and its remaining $(L - 1)$ elements equal to zero. Given these definitions, the following properties can be proved (here, \mathbf{P}_i indicates the i th property):

- **P1:** $\mathbf{x}^T \delta_{L,l} = x_l$
- **P2:** $\delta_{L,l}^T \mathbf{A} \delta_{L,l'} = a_{l,l'}$
- **P3:** if $z_l = x_l y_l$ for any l , then $\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{x} \odot \mathbf{y}$
- **P4:** if $a_{l,l'} = x_l y_{l'}$, for any l and l' , then $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{xy}^T$

Our derivations start with substituting the expression of \mathbf{h} (16) in the RHS of (26) and evaluating the partial derivative of the resulting expression with respect to the scalar frequency \tilde{f}_{τ_l}

(with $l = 0, 1, \dots, L - 1$); this yields

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \tilde{f}_{\tau_l}} = -2\Re \left\{ \tilde{\mathbf{a}}^H \delta_{L,l} \delta_{L,l}^T \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{\tau}}^H (\hat{\mathbf{h}} - \mathbf{B}\tilde{\mathbf{a}}) \right\}, \quad (37)$$

where $\dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{\tau}}^H$ is an $(MN) \times L$ matrix, whose l th column contains the partial derivative of the l th column of \mathbf{B} (see (18) with $(\mathbf{f}_{\tau}, \mathbf{f}_{\nu}) = (\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{\tau}, \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{\nu})$), with respect to \tilde{f}_{τ_l} . The partial derivative of \mathcal{L} (26) with respect to the scalar frequency \tilde{f}_{ν_l} (with $l = 0, 1, \dots, L - 1$) can be computed in a similar way; this results in

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \tilde{f}_{\nu_l}} = -2\Re \left\{ \tilde{\mathbf{a}}^H \delta_{L,l} \delta_{L,l}^T \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{\nu}}^H (\hat{\mathbf{h}} - \mathbf{B}\tilde{\mathbf{a}}) \right\}, \quad (38)$$

where $\dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{\nu}}^H$ is an $(MN) \times L$ matrix, whose l th column contains the partial derivative of the l th column of \mathbf{B} (see (18) with $(\mathbf{f}_{\tau}, \mathbf{f}_{\nu}) = (\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{\tau}, \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{\nu})$) with respect to \tilde{f}_{ν_l} . Given the partial derivatives in (37) and (38), the gradient vector $\nabla_{\mathcal{L}}(\tilde{\mathbf{a}}, \tilde{\mathbf{f}})$ (having length equal to $2L$) can be obtained, since

$$\nabla_{\mathcal{L}}(\tilde{\mathbf{a}}, \tilde{\mathbf{f}}) \triangleq \left[\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \tilde{f}_{\tau_0}}, \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \tilde{f}_{\tau_1}}, \dots, \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \tilde{f}_{\tau_{L-1}}}, \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \tilde{f}_{\nu_0}}, \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \tilde{f}_{\nu_1}}, \dots, \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \tilde{f}_{\nu_{L-1}}} \right]^T. \quad (39)$$

Exploiting the property **P1** in both (37) and (38) and the property **P3** in (39) easily leads to (29).

The evaluation of the $(2L) \times (2L)$ Hessian matrix $\ddot{\mathbf{H}}_{\mathcal{L}}(\tilde{\mathbf{a}}, \tilde{\mathbf{f}})$ requires computing the partial derivatives of \mathcal{L} (26) with respect to the couple of variables $(\tilde{f}_{\tau_l}, \tilde{f}_{\tau_{l'}})$, $(\tilde{f}_{\tau_l}, \tilde{f}_{\nu_{l'}})$, $(\tilde{f}_{\nu_l}, \tilde{f}_{\tau_{l'}})$ and $(\tilde{f}_{\nu_l}, \tilde{f}_{\nu_{l'}})$. Following the same line of reasoning as the one illustrated for the evaluation of the gradient of \mathcal{L} , it can be easily shown that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{L}}{\partial \tilde{f}_{\tau_l} \partial \tilde{f}_{\tau_{l'}}} &= -2\Re \left\{ \tilde{\mathbf{a}}^H \delta_{L,l} \delta_{L,l'}^T \ddot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{\tau}, \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{\tau}}^H (\hat{\mathbf{h}} - \mathbf{B}\tilde{\mathbf{a}}) \right\} \\ &+ 2\Re \left\{ \tilde{\mathbf{a}}^H \delta_{L,l} \delta_{L,l'}^T \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{\tau}}^H \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{\tau}}^H \delta_{L,l'} \delta_{L,l}^T \tilde{\mathbf{a}} \right\}, \quad (40) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{L}}{\partial \tilde{f}_{\tau_l} \partial \tilde{f}_{\nu_{l'}}} &= -2\Re \left\{ \tilde{\mathbf{a}}^H \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l} \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l'}^T \ddot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{f}_\tau, \tilde{f}_\nu}^H (\hat{\mathbf{h}} - \mathbf{B}\tilde{\mathbf{a}}) \right\} \\ &+ 2\Re \left\{ \tilde{\mathbf{a}}^H \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l} \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l'}^T \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{f}_\tau}^H \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{f}_\nu} \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l'} \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l'}^T \tilde{\mathbf{a}} \right\}, \quad (41) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{L}}{\partial \tilde{f}_{\nu_l} \partial \tilde{f}_{\tau_{l'}}} &= -2\Re \left\{ \tilde{\mathbf{a}}^H \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l} \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l'}^T \ddot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{f}_\nu, \tilde{f}_\tau}^H (\hat{\mathbf{h}} - \mathbf{B}\tilde{\mathbf{a}}) \right\} \\ &+ 2\Re \left\{ \tilde{\mathbf{a}}^H \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l} \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l'}^T \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{f}_\nu}^H \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{f}_\tau} \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l'} \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l'}^T \tilde{\mathbf{a}} \right\} \quad (42) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{L}}{\partial \tilde{f}_{\nu_l} \partial \tilde{f}_{\nu_{l'}}} &= -2\Re \left\{ \tilde{\mathbf{a}}^H \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l} \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l'}^T \ddot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{f}_\nu, \tilde{f}_\nu}^H (\hat{\mathbf{h}} - \mathbf{B}\tilde{\mathbf{a}}) \right\} \\ &+ 2\Re \left\{ \tilde{\mathbf{a}}^H \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l} \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l'}^T \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{f}_\nu}^H \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{f}_\nu} \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l'} \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l'}^T \tilde{\mathbf{a}} \right\}. \quad (43) \end{aligned}$$

Given equations (40)-(43), the $(2L) \times (2L)$ Hessian matrix $\ddot{\mathbf{H}}_{\mathcal{L}}(\tilde{\mathbf{a}}, \tilde{\mathbf{f}})$ can be easily put in the form (30), by exploiting:

- 1) **P1** for all the terms $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}^H \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l}$ and $\boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l'}^T \tilde{\mathbf{a}}$ in (40)-(43);
- 2) **P1** for the terms $\boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l'}^T \ddot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{f}_\tau, \tilde{f}_\tau}^H \mathbf{y}$, $\boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l'}^T \ddot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{f}_\tau, \tilde{f}_\nu}^H \mathbf{y}$, $\boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l'}^T \ddot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{f}_\nu, \tilde{f}_\tau}^H \mathbf{y}$ and $\boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l'}^T \ddot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{f}_\nu, \tilde{f}_\nu}^H \mathbf{y}$, in (40), (41), (42) and (43), respectively (here, $\mathbf{y} \triangleq \hat{\mathbf{h}} - \mathbf{B}\tilde{\mathbf{a}}$);
- 3) **P2** for the terms $\boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l}^T \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{f}_\tau}^H \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{f}_\tau} \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l'}$, $\boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l}^T \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{f}_\tau}^H \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{f}_\nu} \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l'}$, $\boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l}^T \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{f}_\nu}^H \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{f}_\tau} \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l'}$ and $\boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l}^T \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{f}_\nu}^H \dot{\mathbf{B}}_{\tilde{f}_\nu} \boldsymbol{\delta}_{L,l'}$, in (40), (41), (42) and (43), respectively.
- 4) **P3** and **P4** in the resulting expressions.

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